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Undergraduate Thesis

Analysis and Comparison of Traditional Network and Software Defined Networking (SDN)

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ABSTRACT

This thesis examines the architectural differences and performance of Traditional Networks (TN) and Software-Defined Networking (SDN), focusing on latency (RTT), jitter, recovery time, and the ability to enforce bandwidth limits. TN relies on distributed control and device-local configuration, whereas SDN separates the control and data planes, enabling centralized, programmable management. To evaluate both paradigms under comparable conditions, TN was implemented in GNS3 using router/switch forwarding, and SDN was emulated in Mininet with a Ryu controller. Three representative topologies—star, linear, and tree—were tested. Measurements employed ping for RTT, iperf3 for throughput and UDP jitter, and controlled link failures to quantify recovery time.

A key objective was to assess bandwidth limitation. In the SDN environment, priority-based policies were applied to allocate fixed capacities to service groups and per-host ceilings; measured throughputs adhered closely to these configured caps. In the TN baseline, where no hop-by-hop QoS policing or shaping was deployed, throughput varied opportunistically and could not be constrained to a deterministic ceiling across the end-to-end path.

Results show that SDN consistently achieves lower RTT and reduced jitter across all topologies and restores connectivity markedly faster after failures due to controller-driven path recompilation. Moreover, SDN provides enforceable, fine-grained bandwidth control that was not attainable in the tested TN configuration. Although the study is limited to simulated environments and a single controller, the findings offer reproducible evidence that SDN delivers superior flexibility, programmability, and operational efficiency for modern network deployments.

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CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

This chapter presents the traditional network, the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) paradigm with its application areas, and the traffic-engineering challenges that motivate this study. The first section describes the components of the traditional network and its limitations. The second section provides a concise overview of SDN and its advantages over the traditional approach. The third section outlines representative application domains of SDN. The final section summarizes related research and identifies the gap addressed by this thesis.

1.1 Background of the Study

The development of networking technologies has dramatically transformed the way people, businesses, and governments communicate and exchange information. In the early stages, computer networks were relatively simple, consisting of a limited number of interconnected devices. However, as the number of users and applications increased, networks grew in complexity and scale. Traditional networks, which rely heavily on hardware-based devices such as routers, switches, and firewalls, were designed to handle communication by tightly coupling the control plane and the data plane within the same device. This approach provided reliability but also introduced significant challenges in terms of scalability, flexibility, and management.

As organizations moved toward cloud computing, big data, and the Internet of Things (IoT), the demand for dynamic, flexible, and programmable networks has grown rapidly. Traditional networks often require manual configuration of each device, making them prone to human error, time-consuming to manage, and costly to scale. Moreover, adapting to new policies or traffic demands in traditional networks is difficult because changes must be applied device by device.

To address these issues, Software-Defined Networking (SDN) has emerged as a promising solution. SDN introduces a new architecture that separates the control plane from the data plane. Instead of relying on distributed control within each device, SDN employs a centralized controller (such as Ryu) that manages the flow of traffic across the entire network. This separation enables programmability, allowing network administrators to configure, manage, and optimize network resources through software rather than manual hardware configurations. As a result, SDN provides agility, automation, cost efficiency, and adaptability compared to traditional networks.

This thesis investigates both traditional and SDN-based network architectures by implementing them in a simulated environment using Mininet and analyzing key performance parameters such as bandwidth, latency, packet loss, recovery time, and reconfiguration time. Through this analysis, the study aims to highlight the advantages and limitations of each approach, providing valuable insights into the potential of SDN as a replacement or complement to traditional networking methods.

Figure 1.1 Comparison of Traditional Network and SDN

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite the success of traditional networks in providing connectivity for decades, their rigid architecture poses limitations in the modern digital era. Network traffic continues to grow exponentially due to emerging technologies such as cloud

computing, 5G, and IoT. Traditional networks, with their hardware-dependent configurations, often fail to meet the demands of rapid scalability and dynamic control. Issues such as high operational costs, complex troubleshooting, and difficulty in traffic optimization remain persistent problems.

Software-Defined Networking, on the other hand, offers promising solutions to these problems. However, SDN also faces challenges of its own, including controller bottlenecks, security vulnerabilities, and integration with legacy systems. While SDN is highly programmable, it introduces a single point of failure at the controller, which raises concerns about reliability in large-scale deployments.

Therefore, there is a need to conduct a systematic comparison between traditional and SDN-based networks to understand which approach performs better in different scenarios. This research addresses the gap by providing experimental analysis of both architectures under similar conditions, focusing on key network performance indicators.

1.3. Aim and Objectives

The thesis aims to design, implement, and compare the performance of traditional networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) using simulation tools.

In order to achieve this, the research work is divided into the following distinct objectives.

- To understand the differences between traditional network and SDN.
- To understand and implement both traditional and SDN topologies.
- To analyze the comprehensive implementation of tools like GNS3, Mininet, Open Flow Open vSwitch etc.
- To evaluate performance metrics such as bandwidth, latency, packet loss, recovery time, and reconfiguration time in both architectures.
- To analyze the experimental results and compare the efficiency, flexibility, and scalability of traditional and SDN networks.
- To provide practical recommendations for organizations considering migration from traditional to SDN-based networks.

1.4. Scope of the Thesis

The scope of this thesis is limited to a comparative performance analysis between traditional networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) using a simulated environment. The study relies on Mininet as the primary network emulator and the Ryu controller as the SDN control platform. The chosen environment allows for controlled testing and repeatability of experiments, which makes it suitable for academic research.

The research specifically focuses on small-to-medium scale topologies, which are practical to simulate and analyze within the available computational resources. It does not attempt to replicate extremely large or global-scale networks, since such implementations would require specialized hardware and infrastructure. Instead, the goal is to capture performance characteristics that can reasonably reflect how traditional and SDN architectures behave under comparable conditions.

Performance evaluation is limited to a selected set of key networking parameters, including:

- Bandwidth – the data transfer capacity of the network, measured using iperf.
- Latency – the time taken for packets to travel from source to destination, measured using ping.
- Packet Loss – the rate of dropped packets during transmission.
- Recovery Time – the time needed for the network to recover after a failure.

By focusing on these parameters, the study aims to provide insights into the operational efficiency, flexibility, and reliability of both architectures. However, other performance metrics such as energy efficiency, large-scale security testing, or cost analysis are beyond the scope of this work and may be addressed in future research.

Another important limitation of this study is that it is conducted entirely in a virtualized environment. While Mininet is highly accurate in modeling network behavior, it cannot fully replicate the complexity of real-world environments such as unpredictable traffic, hardware-specific constraints, or large-scale deployments. Therefore, while the results are valid within the scope of the simulation, they may vary if implemented on physical infrastructures.

In summary, this study provides a baseline comparative analysis of traditional and SDN networks in a controlled simulation environment. The findings will serve as a reference for future research and may guide organizations considering the adoption of SDN. However, the study does not claim to cover every aspect of networking, and the conclusions are bound by the scale, tools, and performance parameters chosen.

1.5. Outline of Thesis

Basically, the thesis is divided into five chapters. Chapter one introduces the study by presenting the background and motivation, problem statement, research aim and objectives, and the scope and significance of the work. Chapter two reviews related literature on traditional networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN), compares prior approaches, and identifies the research gap. Chapter Three details the implementation, including the network designs, toolchain (e.g., Mininet and Ryu), and configuration steps for both traditional and SDN topologies. Chapter Four reports the test methodology and results for bandwidth, latency, jitter/packet loss, and recovery time, and provides a comparative analysis between the two architectures. Chapter Five presents the discussion and conclusion, highlights the key contributions, and outlines directions for future work.

1.6 Summary

This chapter motivates and frames the study by contrasting traditional, device-centric networking with Software-Defined Networking (SDN). It explains how the growth of cloud, IoT, and modern traffic demands exposes limits in distributed, hardware-configured networks, and it introduces SDN's separation of control and data planes as a programmable alternative. The chapter states the problem and sets the aim: to design, implement, and compare both paradigms in a controlled simulation, evaluating core performance indicators—bandwidth, latency, packet loss, recovery time, and reconfiguration time. It then lists the research objectives and defines scope and limitations: experiments are conducted in a virtual environment—primarily Mininet with a Ryu controller—on small-to-medium topologies, prioritizing repeatability over large-scale realism. Together, these elements establish the rationale, goals, and boundaries that guide the remainder of the thesis.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter presents the traditional network, the SDN network with its application area, and the traffic engineering domain problems exposed in the existing SDN architecture. The first section presents the traditional network's components and its challenges. The second section covers a brief overview of SDN and its advantages over the traditional network. The third section starts with a focus on the application areas of SDN. Finally, the last section reviews the related research studies and its current work.

2.1. Traditional Network

Ethernet switch is one of the most commonly used network elements to serve as the network connection point for hosts in Local Area Networks (LANs). It uses hardware addresses, MAC addresses, to forward the frame at the data link layer of the (Open Systems Interconnection) OSI model. The switch operates at the data link layer of the OSI model to create a separate collision domain of every switch interface. Each network element connected to a switch interface can transmit and receive the data simultaneously.

The switch forwards data frames based on the Media Access Control (MAC) table. When a frame arrives at a switch, the switch will put the source MAC address and correspond incoming interface number in the MAC table as the basis for forwarding new frames. Then the destination MAC address will be inspected. If a switch not having an entry for the destination MAC address in its table, it floods all of its interfaces with a broadcast message requesting the location of the MAC address. Each connected switch relays this broadcast message to all of its neighbors until eventually a switch reply. This reply is traced back to the original switch that initially requested the location of the MAC address and MAC tables are updated by each switch along the way to reflect the newly discovered MAC address.

If the destination MAC address is a multicast address or unknown unicast, it will forward the frame to all the interfaces except the incoming interface. Otherwise,

the frame will be forwarded to the specific interface according to the MAC table. When the 10 switch floods a frame to the network, it may create the traffic loop in the network whose topology consists of loops. To solve this, the legacy switch usually uses a spanning tree protocol that blocks some interfaces so that the resulting logical LAN topology is a tree. Through the spanning tree protocol, traffic loops can be prevented.

2.1.1. Challenges of Traditional Network

Mobile devices and their contents, cloud computing, and virtualization, have highlighted the need for a new network architecture that the industry is trying to satisfy. This change was necessary because the old network architecture was based on hierarchy, which was built on tiers of Ethernet switches arranged in a tree structure. This kind of architecture was unsuitable for nowadays dynamic computing and storage needs of enterprise data centers, campuses and carrier environments are not satisfied. All this is a challenge for traditional networks.

Traditional networks were static in nature and were manually configured based on service requests. Thus, will make it challenging to control the network in both their management and their operation. Traditional networking functions are mainly implemented in dedicated networking devices such as switches, routers, and application delivery controllers. As for network management, networking devices have to be configured on a per-device basis using vendor-specific proprietary interfaces. While network administrators need to define high-level policies and apply them over the whole network, these interfaces only allow low-level configuration of individual devices. And although tools for centralized management exist, they serve rather for monitoring of the network than for its configuration as a whole.

Concerning network operation, typical networking devices use routing protocols to fill their forwarding tables, but may also allow for network administrators to manually configure additional rules. These rules may, for example, provide application port filtering or different treatment for particular quality-of-service classes. Unfortunately, there is no protocol to automatically distribute these more complex policies over the network.

With packet forwarding based only on destination addresses or statically defined rules, the network cannot react to the dynamics of the traffic or to the occurring abnormalities. Be it peak loads, applications with high demands for Quality of Service, or applications requiring high bandwidth, with the static setting, the network has no

instruments to appropriately utilize its resources unless equipped with specialized devices like load balancers.

To be fitted for demands of modern deployments, in both campuses and data centers, a network should provide means for automation, so it could react to occurring events on its own and efficiently use available resources while ensuring resilience. Such a network should also be virtualized in order to provide a high-level abstraction for convenient management of the network regardless of the underlying physical layer and its specifics.

Software-defined networking, further described in the next session, is assured to bring a solution to the various problems networking is facing today.

2.2. Software Defined Networking (SDN)

A new networking architecture called Software-Defined Networking (SDN) emerged in the early 2010s. The essence of SDN is changing the way of the network to change the way of creating and managing the network. The main characteristic of the SDN architecture is that decoupling the control plane and data plan and abstracting from each other. A consequence of this decoupling is lead to greater flexibility in network management. Since networking devices such as switches and routers simply act as the data plane's forwarding devices, the controller at the control plane centrally controls the devices by determining the forwarding rules according to the network condition. Unlike traditional traffic management, instead of managing network traffic at the per-hop level from one host to the next, SDN works with the flow level from source to destination. The controller determines the path and reserves the resources from source to destination when a flow is admitted. This design leads to global views and management of network traffic, which makes it possible to coordinate QoS guarantees and forwarding decisions at larger scales. Overall, SDN makes network management much simpler by providing dynamic reconfiguration of network devices in the data plane and by centralizing flow coordination in a network to minimize resource contention.

2.2.1. SDN Reference Architecture

An SDN consists of three layers: application layer, control layer, and data plane layer. A detailed explanation of the key layers is:

Data (forwarding) Plane: In a bottom-up fashion, the data plane is the forwarding device interconnected through wired or wireless means. The data plane's purpose is to forward network traffic as efficiently as possible based on a certain set of forwarding rules which are instructed by the control plane. SDN architecture removes the forwarding intelligence from the networking hardware and moving these functionalities to the control plane. One-way traditional OpenFlow switches (i.e., the data plane) provide these forwarding properties is through Ternary Content-Addressable Memory (TCAM) hardware. The forwarding elements and SDN controller communicate using the southbound interface called OpenFlow. At present, the Open Flow protocol, serves as a standard southbound communication protocol supported by several vendors including the ONF.

Control Plane: The SDN control plane, often referred to as the controller, is the component that programs and manages forwarding devices over the southbound interface. The control plane is responsible for making decisions on how traffic would be routed through the network from the source node to destination node based on end-user application requirements and communicating the computed network policies to the data plane. The controller becomes the centralized brain in the network and it works as a network operating system (NOS). An SDN controller translates different application requirements such as the need for QoS, traffic prioritizing, bandwidth management, etc. into relevant forwarding rules which are communicated to data plane network forwarding elements. SDN becomes possible to manipulate flow tables in individual elements in real-time based on network performance and service requirements by using network programmability through the control plane. In brief, the controller gives a clear and centralized view of the underlying network giving a powerful network management tool to fine-tune network performance. Furthermore, the control plane provides the network abstraction that can be used by network applications to achieve high-level functionality in the network.

Application Plane: The application plane includes network management applications such as firewalls, routing, and other applications that enforce the policy. An abstract view of the underlying network is presented to applications via a controller northbound API. The level of abstraction may include network parameters such as throughput, delay, and availability. Applications in return request connectivity between end nodes and once the application or network services communicate these requirements to the SDN controller, it correspondingly

configures individual network elements in the data plane for efficient traffic forwarding. Centralized management of network elements provides additional leverage to administrators giving them vital network statistics to adapt service quality and customize network topology as needed. For example, during periods of high network utilization certain bandwidth consuming services such as large file transfers, video streaming, etc. can be load-balanced over dedicated channels. In other scenarios, such as during an emergency like fire alarms service such as VoIP can take control of the network i.e., telephony taking precedence over everything else. Figure 2.1 illustrates a simplified scheme for SDN.

Figure 2.1 Simplified SDN Scheme

2.2.2. SDN Controller for Control Plane

In the SDN architecture, the controller works as a brain of the network and it is where the control plane resides as depicted in Figure 2.1. A controller is a software that serves as a central control point that overlooks the network and through which applications can access and manage the network. When the controller is said to be a central point of the network, it is only meant to be logically centralized. The controller software is typically deployed on a high-performance server machine, but to distribute

the load or to ensure high availability and resilience, more servers may be involved and connected in various topologies. The controller is responsible for the following tasks:

- **Device discovery:** the controller takes care of the discovery of switches and end-user devices, and their management.
- **Network topology tracking:** the controller investigates the links interconnecting devices in the network and keeps a view of the underlying resources.
- **Flow management:** the controller maintains a database mirroring the flow entries configured in the switches it manages.
- **Statistics tracking:** the controller gathers and keeps per-flow statistics from the switches.

It is important to emphasize that the controller does neither control the network in any way nor does it replace any networking devices. Even the basic switching or routing functionality has to be provided by specific applications that approach the network through the controller.

2.2.3. Software Switch for the Data Plane

A summary of command software switches which are also used for experimentation and new service development were given in Table 3.2. Detailed expression of two well-known software switches presently available is present in the below sub-session.

Table 2.1: Common OpenFlow Software Switches

Switch	Implementation	Description
Open vSwitch	C/Python	OpenFlow stack that is used both as a virtual switch and ported to multiple hardware platforms
Ofsoftswitch13	C/C++	User-space software switches implementation

2.2.3.1. Overview of Open vSwitch

OpenFlow may be deployed either at the software level or hardware level onto forwarding devices in the data plane. More specifically, many well-known networking vendors like Cisco, Juniper, IBM, and HP, support OpenFlow, either with a dedicated

product or running an OpenFlow software switch on top of their switches. Open vSwitch is one of the software switches implemented to support OpenFlow which can be installed to enable OpenFlow. Open vSwitch is a multilayer software switch that is intended to function as a virtual switch. Open vSwitch supports all versions of OpenFlow from 1.0 to 1.5 as well as GRE tunneling, queues, and so forth. The core of Open vSwitch is the switch daemon (ovs-vswitchd). This daemon tracks statistical queries and flow management internally on the switch, and also handles communication with external devices and services. For management and configuration, in parallel with connectivity to the OpenFlow controller, it is possible to configure and control the Open vSwitch via ovs-vsctl and ovs-ofctl. ovs-vsctl is a command line tool to configure ovs-vswitchd by providing an interface to its configuration database, while ovs-ofctl is a command line tool for monitoring and administering Open vSwitch. Moreover, ovsdbmonitor is a tool to view flow tables and databases of Open vSwitch. As illustrated in Figure 2.2, ovsdb-server relies on the OVS Management protocol to communicate with Remote Open vSwitch db (a database maintained by Open vSwitch to store its information). Unlike flow entries in the switch, the OVSDb configuration is preserved even after the switch restarts.

Figure 2.2 Simple Open vSwitch Architecture

2.2.3.2. Overview of OfSoftSwitch (CPqD)

The OfSoftSwitch13 (CPqD) is another switch that is widely used in the research community. It is an experimental switch forked from the Ericsson Traffic SoftSwitch implementation with changes in the forwarding plane to support OF1.3. The Ofsoftswitch13 is running in the user space and it also supports multiple

OpenFlow versions. Ofsoftswitch13 supports a variety of OpenFlow features but it has recently run into some compatibility issues with the latest versions of Linux (Ubuntu 14.0 and beyond) and developer support has also stagnated. It comes packaged with the following tools to control and manage the data plane:

- OfDatapath: The switch implementation.
- OfLib: A library for converting to/from OF1.3 wire formats.
- DPCTL: Console tool to configure the switch.
- OfProtocol: A secure communication channel with the controller.

All this makes it a complete alternative to the OVS. However, the authors of the switch state the following, “Despite the fact the switch is still popular for adventurers trying to implement own changes to OpenFlow, support now is on a best-effort basis. Currently, there are lots of complaints about performance degradation, broken features, and installation problems.”. The switch still has one of the best supports for OF1.3 features among the available soft-switches, specifically the optional features like meter tables, etc., which makes it an attractive candidate to get hands-on with. Additionally, the soft switch supports a management utility called Data Path Control (Dpctl), to directly control the Open Flow switch including the flow addition and deletion, query switch statistics and modify flow table configurations.

2.3. Differences between Traditional Network and SDN

In the traditional network model, the control plane and the data plane are bundled inside the networking devices. The data plane tells the incoming traffic where it needs to go. The location of the control plane is particularly inconvenient because administrators do not have easy access to dictate the traffic flow.

Figure 2.3 Architecture of Traditional Network and SDN

In the SDN network model, SDN breaks the vertical integration of the control plane and data plane by separating the network's control logic from the underlying routers and switches that forward the traffic. As a consequence, network switches become simple forwarding devices and the control logic is implemented in a logically centralized controller simplifying policy enforcement and network configuration. Figure 2.3 depicted the comparison of traditional network and SDN network architecture.

Three main differences between traditional networking and SDN architecture are as follows:

- SDN controller has a northbound interface to communicate with applications through application programming interfaces (APIs). This allows application developers to program the network directly while traditional networking works through using protocols.
- To establish connections and run properly, traditional networking relies on physical infrastructure. Meanwhile, SDN is a software-based network, which allows the network users to control virtual-level network resource allocation via the control plane and to determine network paths and proactively configure network services.
- In traditional networking, the control plane is located in a switch or router, which is particularly inconvenient for the administrators to access it to order the traffic flow. Compared with the traditional networking, SDN has more ability to communicate with devices throughout the network. SDN offers administrators the right to control traffic flow from a centralized user interface and allows resources provisioning from a centralized location. It virtualizes the entire network and gives users more control over their network capabilities.

Table 2.2 The Characteristics of Traditional Network and SDN Architectures

Characteristics	SDN	Traditional Network
Network Control Centralized	✓	✗
Programmability	✓	✗
Flexibility of Network	✓	✗
Complex Control Network	✗	✓
Performance Improved	✓	✗
Configuration of Error-Prone	✗	✓
Management Enhanced	✓	✗
Configuration Efficiency	✓	✗
Easy to use and implement	✓	✗

2.3.1. Advantages of Traditional Network

Despite their limitations, traditional networks continue to provide several advantages that explain their long-standing use in enterprises, Internet Service Providers (ISPs), and global infrastructures.

The following are the advantages of traditional network.

- **Stability and Maturity**

Traditional networks are built on decades of research, deployment, and refinement. Their technologies such as IP routing, Ethernet switching, and MPLS are widely understood, tested, and standardized. This stability ensures predictable performance and makes them reliable for mission-critical environments.

- **Wide Compatibility and Interoperability**

Because traditional networking protocols are standardized, devices from different vendors typically interoperate smoothly. Organizations can build networks with routers, switches, and firewalls from multiple suppliers without major compatibility issues.

- **Proven Reliability**

Distributed control ensures that decision-making is spread across network devices. If one device fails, others continue to operate independently, reducing the risk of total network failure. This inherent redundancy provides strong reliability.

- **Availability of Skilled Workforce**

As traditional networks have been around for decades, there is a large pool of trained professionals who are familiar with configuration, troubleshooting, and management of legacy systems. This makes it easier for organizations to maintain such networks.

- **Incremental Upgrades**

Organizations can expand traditional networks gradually by adding more devices, without the need for radical architectural changes. This incremental approach reduces upfront costs and disruptions.

2.3.2. Advantages of SDN

The rapid development of new trends in networking, such as server virtualization, cloud services, a vast diversity of mobile data applications, etc., determines the need for new network architectures to manage flexibly with the

changing environment. The new emerging technology, SDN has several advantages over the traditional network.

The most common specific advantages of SDN are as follows:

- Centralized Control and Visibility

SDN centralizes network intelligence in a controller, which provides a global view of the entire network. This simplifies management, as administrators can enforce policies, optimize traffic, and monitor performance from a single point of control.

- Programmability and Automation

One of SDN's greatest strengths is programmability. Network behavior can be dynamically adjusted through software, allowing rapid changes without manual reconfiguration of each device. This automation reduces human error and speeds up deployment of new services.

- Flexibility and Agility

Unlike traditional networks, where changes are slow and complex, SDN enables quick adaptation to shifting traffic patterns or application demands. This agility is critical for cloud computing, big data applications, and dynamic enterprise environments.

- Efficient Resource Utilization

Through features like network slicing and traffic engineering, SDN ensures that bandwidth and resources are allocated where they are most needed. This leads to improved Quality of Service (QoS) and better overall network efficiency.

- Simplified Troubleshooting and Monitoring

With centralized visibility, SDN makes it easier to detect and resolve faults. Administrators can trace traffic paths, analyze bottlenecks, and deploy fixes through software, rather than physically checking each device.

- Faster Innovation

Because new functions can be introduced via software, SDN accelerates innovation. Developers can design and test new protocols or applications without waiting for hardware vendors to release updates. This enables continuous improvement and faster adoption of emerging technologies.

The particular advantages of SDN will typically vary from network to network, however, there are benefits from network abstraction and the agility it offers for network administration and automation. The most ideal approach to take advantage of SDN is to assess the network components and infrastructure to decide whether SDN can help address issues, for example, resource availability, virtualization, and network security. The significant advantage of adopting the SDN is the world's largest networks such as Facebook, Yahoo, NTT Communication Deutsche Telekom, Microsoft, Google that have supported SDN based architecture.

2.4. SDN Application Areas

Currently, SDN has found a great deal of applicability in a wide range of network application areas. SDN provides the opportunities for large scale network like data center network with the help of its real-time programmable framework. Moreover, mobile operators have also shown intense interest in bringing the technology to 5G/LTE mobile networks to allow simplified yet rapid development and deployment of new services. Also, SDN is widely used by social networking websites (Facebook, Twitter, Google plus etc.) and large database search engines (Google, Yahoo, Ask etc.). The key applications area of SDN and some are highlighted in the following sub-sessions.

Some widely-used applications of SDN are organized as follows:

- **Software-Defined Mobile Network (SDMN)**
SDN improves the management of mobile networks by separating the control and data planes. This enables higher flexibility, scalability, and efficient handling of mobile communication traffic.
- **Internet-Based Networking (IBN)**
Through software interfaces, SDN allows internet-driven applications to be deployed and managed more easily. This reduces reliance on traditional hardware-based configurations and provides faster adaptability.
- **Reliable Group Data Delivery (RGDD)**
SDN supports optimized routing and efficient multicast/broadcast mechanisms, ensuring reliable and timely delivery of group data to multiple users or devices.

- **Agile Operations**
By centralizing network intelligence, SDN enables quick adjustments to network operations. This agility supports dynamic business requirements and improves service delivery.
- **Simplified Network Setup**
With centralized control, SDN reduces the complexity of initial network setup and configuration. This makes deployment faster, easier, and less error-prone.
- **Corporate Security**
SDN strengthens enterprise security by allowing centralized monitoring and policy enforcement. It also enables rapid detection and response to emerging threats.

Figure 2.4 Top Applications of SDN

2.4.1. Traffic Engineering

Traffic engineering (TE) is a key networking area for measuring and managing the network traffic, designing reasonable routing mechanisms to guide network traffic for improving utilization of network resources, and meeting required quality of service (QoS) of the network. Therefore, the path control process through which the traffic is handled in TE. There are many reasons why network managers need to influence the characteristics of a path, one of them is the use of optimization of network resources. To optimize the network resources, network managers must try to avoid the situation of certain parts of congestion when others are underutilized.

Another important reason is to find the path with certain limitations-constraints that can support the proper performance for some high priority flows. For example, the

path for the delay-sensitive flow like VoIP should not be long delay links. Through this process of TE new services are offered with extensive QoS guarantees and investments decline in new network resources such as bandwidth, by optimizing the use of existing ones. The underlying network architecture is required on today's internet applications to be scalable for a large amount of traffic and to react in real-time. Also, the demand that the user has been also growing and the user now wants to be connected with everything, constantly.

Moreover, each application and services generate their own characteristic flow and they shared the overall network bandwidth competitively. Therefore, the network architecture should be able to classify a diversity of network traffic types from different applications and to provide a suitable and particular service for each traffic type in a very short time period. It is not easy to make sure that to efficiently handle and steer all those varieties of traffic types in order to meet their specific performance for each specific application. Therefore, new networking architectures with more intelligent and efficient TE tools are urgently needed.

Figure 2.5 The Components of Traffic Engineering

Figure 2.5 illustrates the components of TE. The TE technology based on the SDN comprises two portions: traffic measurement and traffic management. The goal of the traffic measurement is to studies the monitoring, measuring, and acquiring the SDN network's status information in the SDN network. The information includes the status of current topology connection, ports (down or up), various types of packet counters, the counters of the dropped packets, ratios link bandwidths utilization, end-to-end traffic matrices and end-to-end network latency so on. For avoiding network congestions and improving network efficiency, the network status information can be used in validating whether the current network status is current by the administrator and predicting the future traffic trend by analyzing packet counters statistics.

Network management mainly studies how to maintain network availability and how to improve network performance. Network traffic scheduling is an important way to improve QoS performance for the different application traffic. In general, SDN has multiple paths between the source and the destination node, which can be used for traffic scheduling. The controller maintains the global view of the current status of each path in the network using various network measurement technologies mentioned above. Consequently, the network administrator can design a traffic scheduling algorithm to dynamically plan data forwarding paths to meet users' requirements.

Figure 2.6 Traffic Engineering Architecture in SDN

Figure 2.6 illustrates the abstract view of TE architecture in the SDN network. Compared with the traditional networks, the TE mechanism in SDN can be much more efficient and intelligently implemented due to its distinguishing characteristics. More specifically, SDN provides the concept of decoupling between control and forwarding plane, the programmability of network behavior, and global centralized control.

2.4.2. Network Performance Optimizing

Network resource optimization can involve a number of specific optimizations goals, including traffic reduction, blocking reduction, latency reduction, and load balancing. Some of these goals are not exclusive and are closely linked; for example, reducing traffic in the network often results in a reduction in blocking, due to there

being additional capacity available within the network for further traffic. However, there are also other ways to reduce blocking within the network, such as spreading the load across the network in a load balancing approach. These close links between optimization goals are important, as they provide insights into multiple solutions to larger optimization problems. These types of problems often require using multi-objective optimization techniques, in order to achieve the best solution possible. This is because multi-objective optimization allows for a far wider search of solution parameters than normal optimization techniques.

With the existing optimization goals in mind, it should be clear that each characteristic being improved could benefit specific scenarios; furthermore, it is important to tailor optimization techniques to the application being utilized on the network. For example, delay-tolerant content delivery would not benefit significantly from latency reduction, but the reduction in traffic would provide improved scalability due to additional capacity being available for further demands. In addition to this, a reduction in traffic would also reduce transmission costs for any links where cost is linked to usage.

2.4.3. Data Centers and Cloud Environments

Compared with the small scales network, the requirements of TE and policy implementation are really high in the case of large scales network architecture like a datacenter. Generally, increasing network latency and persistent troubleshooting may result not only in undesirable end-user experience but also in substantial effects on the cost penalties for the operators. Due to the significant feature of centralized control framework, the implementation of Datacenter (DC) in SDN can provide the fine-grain network management which makes easier for the network operators to monitor and manage hundreds of network element. For example, Google described four generations of their datacenter networks by using SDN technology in 2015. SDN tied a connection between its geographically distributed data centers from all over the world.

The implementation of SDN in the cloud computing environment delivers a solution for powerful TE to increase service scalability and automated network provisioning. Microsoft public cloud and NTT's software-defined edge gateway automation system are the distinguished examples of SDN deployment in a cloud computing environment.

2.4.4. Campus and High-Speed Networks

The heterogeneous networking technologies integration with a centralized controller and OpenFlow enabled network elements has seen a great deal of applicability in optical high-speed networking. Customer needs for the SDN framework for enterprise networks are urgent due to the diversity of network traffic patterns that require proactive management to adjust network policies and fine-tune performance. Using centralized real-time programmability of SDN, the network may eliminate middleboxes which provide services such as NAT, firewalls, access control and service differentiation solutions and load balancers.

For achieving programmability for the greater network, SDN application, and high speed and campus networking controlled with OpenFlow continue to grow resulting in new as well as hybrid solutions. SDN provides a centralized control plane to effectively monitor the network resources utilization.

2.4.5. Wireless Communications

The SDN paradigm has been ported to mobile communication networks because of the real-time programmability and potential to introduce new applications and services to consumers. A programmable wireless data plane allowed developers to finetune mobile communications performance by offering routing based on flexible MAC and physical address in comparison to the traffic forwarding based on layer 3 logical address. There have been growing efforts to include the SDN layering model in the upcoming 5G mobile communication. There is an opportunity to offer a more modular control and traffic forwarding framework with the use of SDN, user traffic can be separated and routed over different protocols. Similar to information-centric networking, an efficient network resource management scheme is needed to provide maximum utilization network slicing, and guaranteeing fairness among several QoS classes.

Using SDN to maximize energy efficiency in 5G networking has, therefore, been the subject of investigation in several studies. SDN has also been test-implemented in 5G to allow rapid application service provisioning while adhering to stringent QoS requirements. At the more local level such as Wi-Fi access networks, SDN could be used to offer a great deal of ubiquity in connecting to different wireless infrastructures belonging to different providers using user device identity management which is in turn coordinated and proactively managed by the SDN controller.

2.5. Research Challenges

The major research advances can be made in several SDN areas. Although Software-Defined Networking (SDN) presents many advantages over traditional networks, several challenges remain in both academic research and practical implementation. These challenges cover scalability, reliability, security, performance, integration, and real-world validation. A deeper understanding of these issues is necessary to determine whether SDN can fully replace or coexist with traditional networking.

2.5.1. Scalability of SDN controllers

The centralized control model of SDN introduces significant scalability concerns. In small or medium-sized networks, a single controller may be sufficient to handle traffic requests. However, in large-scale networks such as data centers or wide-area enterprise environments, thousands of flows are generated every second. Processing such a high volume of flow requests can overwhelm a single controller, leading to bottlenecks, increased response times, and potential network slowdowns. The challenge lies in designing distributed or hierarchical controller architectures that can scale efficiently while still providing centralized visibility.

2.5.2. Reliability and Single Point of Failure

In traditional networks, decision-making is distributed across routers and switches, which provides redundancy if one device fails. By contrast, SDN relies heavily on the centralized controller. This architecture introduces the risk of a single point of failure. If the controller fails, the entire network can experience disruption, making it less reliable than distributed systems. Ensuring reliability requires mechanisms such as controller replication, fault-tolerant architectures, and dynamic failover strategies, all of which introduce complexity and require further investigation.

2.5.3. Security Concerns and Integration with Latency Networks

Centralization of control in SDN makes the controller a critical target for attackers. If compromised, it could allow malicious control of the entire network. Additionally, the communication between the controller and forwarding devices is vulnerable to attacks such as denial of service, spoofing, or interception. While

traditional networks also face security risks, their distributed nature reduces the impact of a single compromise. In SDN, a single successful attack can have network-wide consequences, making the development of strong security mechanisms essential.

Most organizations have long-standing investments in traditional networking infrastructure. Replacing these systems entirely with SDN is not always feasible due to cost and operational concerns. As a result, hybrid environments—where SDN and traditional networks coexist—are common. However, integrating the two introduces challenges such as protocol compatibility, management complexity, and inconsistent performance. Developing smooth migration strategies and interoperability frameworks is an ongoing challenge in both industry and research.

2.5.4. Performance Trade-offs

SDN offers programmability and flexibility, but these benefits come with performance trade-offs. Since forwarding decisions often rely on the controller, frequent communication between switches and the controller can introduce latency. This delay becomes more noticeable in applications that require real-time performance, such as financial systems or video conferencing. Traditional networks, though less flexible, provide faster hardware-based packet forwarding. Balancing programmability with consistent high performance is a continuing research problem.

2.5.5. Standardization and Interoperability

While protocols such as OpenFlow have provided a foundation for SDN, there is still no universal standard for all aspects of SDN implementation. Different vendors develop their own controllers and interfaces, leading to interoperability issues in multi-vendor networks. This lack of standardization complicates adoption, as organizations often struggle to integrate products from different suppliers. Achieving vendor-neutral standards and widely adopted APIs is a challenge that must be addressed before SDN can achieve widespread deployment.

2.6. Summary

This chapter provided a comprehensive review of traditional networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN), comparing their characteristics, strengths, and limitations. Traditional networks offer proven stability, compatibility, and reliability

but suffer from inflexibility and complexity due to static configurations and vendor-specific interfaces. In contrast, SDN decouples the control and data planes to deliver centralized visibility, programmability, and automation, enabling faster innovation, efficient resource utilization, and dynamic traffic management across diverse environments such as data centers, cloud infrastructures, and 5G networks. The chapter also identified SDN's key challenges—including controller scalability, reliability, security, and integration with legacy systems—underscoring the need for further research and standardization. This review establishes the groundwork for the following experimental analysis by framing both technologies' strengths and weaknesses for evaluation under different topologies and performance metrics.

CHAPTER 3

IMPLEMENTATION PROCESS

This chapter details the methodology and practical implementation used to compare traditional networks with Software-Defined Networking (SDN). Using Mininet for emulation and the Ryu controller for centralized SDN control, both paradigms were built under identical topologies (single, linear, tree, star, and ring). Performance was evaluated with iperf3 and related tools across bandwidth, latency, jitter, packet loss, and recovery time. The chapter introduces the tools and topologies, then explains implementation and testing procedures, and concludes with data collection and analysis methods.

3.1. Tools and Technologies Used

The successful implementation of this study relies on a combination of open-source tools, programming frameworks, and measurement utilities. These tools were selected based on their reliability, compatibility, and suitability for academic research in the field of networking. The following subsections describe each tool and technology used in the experimental setup.

3.1.1. GNS3 (Graphical Network Simulator-3)

GNS3 is an open-source graphical network simulation tool that allows the design and testing of network topologies in a highly interactive environment. It provides support for real networking software images, virtual machines, and simulated devices, making it a powerful platform for both academic research and industry-level training. The advantages of GNS3 include:

- Graphical interface for easy design and visualization of topologies.

- Integration with real device images such as Cisco IOS, enabling more realistic simulations.
- Compatibility with virtual environments, allowing hybrid setups with Mininet and other tools.
- Scalability, as it can be run on a single PC or distributed across multiple servers.

In this thesis, GNS3 was used for designing and planning the network topologies prior to their implementation in Mininet. By using GNS3, the logical arrangement of hosts, switches, and links could be visualized, ensuring correctness and reducing configuration errors during the emulation phase. This step also allowed the researcher to validate topology feasibility and make adjustments before executing experiments in the emulated environment.

3.1. 2. Mininet Network Emulator

To emulate an entire network infrastructure in the SDN environment, Mininet network emulator is used. It is the main tool for Software-Defined Networking testbed environments to design, undergo and verify OpenFlow projects. Mininet provides a high level of flexibility since topologies and new functionalities are programmed using python language. It also provides a scalable prototyping environment, able to manage up to 4000 switches on a regular computer. This is possible due to an OS-level virtualization feature, as well as including processes and network namespaces, that permits to produce completely different and separate instances of network interfaces and routing tables that typically operate the independents of every different.

Mininet mainly allows the hosts, switches, and controllers and it creates a huge network simulation in a single PC. It creates the virtual open flow network which includes SDN controller, OpenFlow software switches, multiple hosts and links in a real or virtual machine. The Mininet tool will work in the different operating systems such as Mac OS, Windows, and Linux. Mostly for the Research part, Linux is preferable. Using Mininet can create the small data center consists of hosts and open flow switches. By implementing this experiment, the output can be achieved.

3.1.2.1. Topologies elements

There are four topology elements that Mininet can create:

- **Link:** emulates a wired connection between two virtual interfaces which act as a fully functional Ethernet port. Packets are delivered through one interface to another. It is possible to configure Traffic Control for the links importing the TCLink library via the Python API.
- **Host:** emulates a Linux computer which is simply a shell process moved into its own namespace, from where commands can be called. Each host has its own virtual Ethernet interface.
- **Switch:** software OpenFlow switches typically provide the identical packet delivery semantics that will be provided by a hardware switch.
- **Controller:** Mininet allows to create controller within the same emulation or to connect the emulated network to an external controller running anywhere there is IP connectivity with the machine where Mininet is running.

3.1.2.2 Command used to create topology in Mininet

To execute Mininet passing a file containing a particular topology, the command **mn** has to be accompanied to the parameter **--topo mytopo** and the parameter **-custom mytopo**, and the name of the file is **simple_topo.py**. The command used to launch a custom network topology is this “root@user:sudo mn -custom ~/mininet/custom simple_topo.py -topo mytopo -controller=remote,ip=127.0.0.2,port=6633”.

The option **--mac** is used to set automatically the host MACs addresses. With **-custom** we indicate the path in which is present the file from which you will take the topology, in this case **mytopo.py**, followed by the command **--topo mytopo** which is the specified name given to the **topo** variable inside the file **simple_topo.py**.

3.1.3. Ryu Controller

In the SDN environment, it is essential to select the controller to conduct the proposed application. In this section, an SDN controller, Ryu will be discussed through that operations flow. The logo of the Ryu controller is dragon and Ryū in

Japanese stands for a dragon. Ryu is usually mentioned as component-based, opensource software-defined by a networking framework. It is supported by NTT's labs and executed entirely in Python. Figure 3.1 below depicts the Ryu framework and its main components.

Figure 3.1 Ryu Framework

In the framework, Ryu provides software components with well-defined APIs. By using these APIs, the network developers can make new network management and control applications. Additionally, Ryu supports multiple southbound protocols for managing devices, like Network Configuration Protocol (NETCONF), OpenFlow, OpenFlow Management and Configuration Protocol (OF-Config), and others. The vital components of the architecture are explained in the sub-session below.

3.1.3.1. Ryu libraries

Ryu supports several libraries and multiple southbound protocols. Relating to southbound protocols, Ryu also supports Open vSwitch Database Management Protocol (OVSDB), OF-Config, NETCONF, Sflow, Netflow, and other third-party protocols. Sflow and Netflow protocols can be used for network traffic measurement by using various methods such as packet sampling and aggregation. The third-party libraries embody Open vSwitch Python binding, the Oslo configuration library and a

Python library for the NETCONF client. With the help of Ryu's packet library, the network developer can analyze and build several protocol packets, like VLAN, MPLS etc.

3.1.3.2. Ryu applications

Ryu application is one of the essential elements since the control logic and behavior is defined in it. Multiple applications are already included in the Ryu framework such as topology, simple switch, firewall, router, etc. Although Ryu applications are implemented and provided various functionalities, they work as the single-threaded entities. Formerly, Ryu applications send asynchronous events to each other. Each Ryu application ordinarily has its own receive queue for possible events, that is especially FIFO to properly preserve the executive order of events.

Furthermore, each application typically includes a thread for properly processing events from the queue. The thread's main loop pops out events from the receive queue and calls the suitable event handler. Therefore, the event handler is naturally called within the context of the event-processing thread, that works in a blocking fashion, i.e., once an event handler is given management, no additional events for the Ryu application are going to be processed till management is returned. The functional architecture of a Ryu application is introduced in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2 Functional Architecture of Ryu Application

3.1.4 OpenFlow Protocol and Controller

The Ryu framework includes an internal controller and the OF protocol which is one of the supported southbound protocols. Ryu supports the OpenFlow protocol starting from version 1.0 to the latest version 1.4. Table 3 summarizes the OpenFlow protocol messages and corresponding API of the Ryu controller.

Table 3.1 OpenFlow Protocol Messages and Corresponding API of Ryu

Controller to switch message	Asynchronous message	Symmetric message	Structures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Handshake • switch-config • flow-table-config modify/read state • queue-config • packet-out, barrier • role-request 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Packet-in • flow-removed port-status • Error. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hello • Echo-Request & Reply • Error • experimenter 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flow-match
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • send_msg API and packet builder APIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • set_ev_cls API and packet parser APIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both Send and Event APIs 	

In the Ryu architecture, the OpenFlow controller is one of the internal events sources and which can manage the switches and events. In addition, Ryu includes an OpenFlow protocol encoder and decoder library.

3.1.5. Iperf

Iperf is a very useful performance measurement tool for measuring the maximum bandwidth available between two nodes. It is utilized in TCP (Transport Control Protocol) and UDP (User Datagram Protocol) connections, through the modulation of various parameters. Mainly Iperf is used for the bandwidth and datagram loss. It mainly uses to calculate the network flow between the two nodes. It must be installed on both nodes, then it must be started as a server on one node, and as a client on the other one. The transmission procedure will take only a few seconds and then you will see the bandwidth.

The following work can be done by using Iperf:

- Measure bandwidth

- in a client-server network, the client generates a UDP flux, with
- a specific bandwidth (BW)
- measure packet loss
- measure jitter
- work in a multicast environment.

3.1.6. Wireshark

Wireshark in common is a common network packet analyzer which can be popularly used on the controller or Mininet host to properly look at OpenFlow exchange message between the controller and individual switches. It adequately captures a packet within the network to instantly show its TCP/IP layer information as detailed as possible, letting to look at its explicit content for purposes like network troubleshooting, security examinations, protocol debugging and network protocol learning.

This tool permits to properly capture live packets from a network interface (physical or virtual), displaying correctly the packet information with elaborate protocol information, and saving all packet captures for additional studies and reliable statistics. The captured information can be analyzed under different criteria, in which the necessary information can be altered by timestamps, TCP/UDP ports, protocols, TCP sessions, and more.

Since Wireshark remain an effective tool that works at user-space, it uses the cap library to permit Wireshark to capture packets at a lower level. This typically allows the capture of packets with a more precise timestamp since there is no additional delay caused by the internal communication process between the user-space and kernel space levels. This research has used the Wireshark dissector provided by a Mininet package, that enables the OpenFlow filter to capture messages and carefully observe their message format in detail, as well as flow entries and group entries.

3.1.7. Software Requirements

The SDN controller, Ryu framework is designed to run on the host computer with a TCP connection to the emulated Mininet network topology. The detailed software versions are shown in Table 3.2.

Table 3.2 Software Requirements

No	Name	Specification
1.	Operation System	Ubuntu 22.04 LTS (64 Bits)
2.	Ryu Controller [Ryu]	Version 4.30
3.	Mininet Emulator [Mininet]	Version 1.3
4.	Open Flow Protocol [OpenFlow]	Version 1.3

3.2. Experimental Topologies

To conduct a fair and systematic comparison between traditional networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN), several standard network topologies were implemented. Each topology was designed to represent different types of network structures commonly found in enterprise, data center, and service provider environments. The experiments of traditional networks were run in GNS-3 software using window10 and experiments of software defined networks were simulated in Mininet using Linux OS on VMware workstation. The selected topologies are:

- Star Topology
- Linear (Bus) Topology
- Tree Topology
- Different Network Topology

By testing both traditional and SDN implementations under these topologies, the study ensures that performance metrics such as bandwidth, latency, packet loss, and recovery time are evaluated across a diverse range of network scenarios.

3.2.1 Star Topology

Star topology shown in Figure.3.3 using SDN network consists of single OpenFlow switch connected to multiple hosts. The OpenFlow switch is connected to OpenFlow controller through secure channel. Star topology in traditional network has single switch connected to multiple hosts but without any controller. In this topology, 8 hosts are taken that are connected to a single switch.

Figure 3.3 Star Topology of SDN and Traditional Network

3.2.2. Linear (Bus) Topology

In linear topology, number of switches are equal to number of hosts. It means that each switch is connected with their particular host. In this topology, 8 hosts are used that are connected to 8 switches in both networks. This topology is shown in Figure.3.4.

Figure 3.4 Linear (Bus) Topology in SDN and Traditional Network

3.2.3. Tree Topology

In tree topology, the switches are organized in binary layout in such a way that switch1 is the source node of tree topology and the leaf nodes are switch4 to switch7 as shown in Figure.3.5. In this topology, 3 switches are used that are linked with 8 hosts. Each leaf node is linked with four hosts in order so that switch4 is linked to host1 and host4, and switch7 is linked to host7 and host8.

Figure 3.5 Tree Topology for SDN and Traditional Network

3.2.4. Two Separate Network Design

Figure 3.6 Two Separate Network Design for SDN and Traditional Network

The first design, shown on the left side of Figure 3.6, represents the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) approach in which the control plane is decoupled from the data plane and placed in a centralized controller. In this architecture, the SDN controller functions as the intelligent decision-making entity that manages the entire network by maintaining a global view of all devices and links. The underlying Open vSwitch (OVS) instances act purely as forwarding devices, responsible only for transmitting packets according to the flow rules provided by the controller. End hosts (h1–h8) are connected to these switches and rely on the controller to establish communication paths. When a

host initiates a connection, the first packet is forwarded to the controller, which computes the optimal route and installs the necessary forwarding rules on each switch along the path. This centralized and programmable mechanism enables flexible traffic management, rapid reconfiguration, and faster failure recovery compared to traditional methods, making the SDN network design highly adaptive and suitable for dynamic network environments.

The second design, illustrated on the right side of Figure 3.6, represents the conventional or traditional network approach, where the control plane and data plane are integrated within the networking devices themselves. In this configuration, the router positioned at the top of the topology performs routing functions by independently maintaining and updating its routing table through static entries or distributed routing protocols such as OSPF or RIP. The connected switches operate at Layer 2 of the OSI model and forward traffic based on MAC addresses within their respective broadcast domains, without centralized programmability. End hosts (Host1–Host8) communicate through the combination of these switches and the router, which forwards packets to the correct destination subnet based on local routing logic. In the event of a link or device failure, the network relies on routing protocol convergence or manual reconfiguration, processes which are inherently slower than SDN's controller-driven recovery. This traditional network design, while stable and well-established, lacks the flexibility and rapid adaptability of SDN, thereby highlighting the contrast between distributed decision-making and centralized control.

3.3. The Test-bed Implementation with Mininet

The SDN controller, Ryu framework is designed to run on the host computer with a TCP connection to the emulated Mininet network topology. The test-bed implementation is structured as illustrated in Figure 3.7.

Firstly, run a simple network topology as shown in Figure 6.4, composed by three clients, h1, h2, and h6 and four servers h3, h4, h5, h7. There are three paths to communicate from the clients to the servers. Hence, path (s1, s3) is the direct communication link and it is the minimum hop count path (shortest path) leaving the other two equal-cost paths (s1, s2, s3) and (s1, s4, s3) as the second shortest. The Mininet script file is shown in the script file below.

Figure 3.7 Simple SDN Network Topology

simple_topo.py

```

#!/usr/bin/env python
from mininet.net import Mininet, CLI
from mininet.node import RemoteController, OVSKernelSwitch, UserSwitch, Host
from mininet.link import TCLink, Link
from mininet.term import makeTerms, makeTerm, runX11
import argparse
import subprocess

net = Mininet(controller=RemoteController, switch=OVSKernelSwitch, link=TCLink)
h1 = net.addHost( 'h1', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:01', ip = '10.0.0.10' )
h2 = net.addHost( 'h2', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:02', ip = '10.0.0.20' )
h3 = net.addHost( 'h3', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:03', ip = '10.0.0.30' )
h4 = net.addHost( 'h4', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:04', ip = '10.0.0.40' )
h5 = net.addHost( 'h5', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:05', ip = '10.0.0.50' )
h6 = net.addHost( 'h6', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:06', ip = '10.0.0.60' )
h7 = net.addHost( 'h7', mac = '00:00:00:00:00:07', ip = '10.0.0.70' )

s1 = net.addSwitch( 's1', cls = OVSKernelSwitch, protocols = 'OpenFlow13' )
s2 = net.addSwitch( 's2', cls = OVSKernelSwitch, protocols = 'OpenFlow13' )
s3 = net.addSwitch( 's3', cls = OVSKernelSwitch, protocols = 'OpenFlow13' )
s4 = net.addSwitch( 's4', cls = OVSKernelSwitch, protocols = 'OpenFlow13' )

net.addLink( s1, s2, port1=1, port2=1 )
net.addLink( s2, s3, port1=2, port2=2 )
net.addLink( s1, s4, port1=2, port2=1 )
net.addLink( s3, s4, port1=3, port2=2 )
net.addLink( s1, s3, port1=3, port2=1 )
net.addLink( s3, h6 )
net.addLink( s3, h4 )
net.addLink( s3, h5 )
net.addLink( s3, h7 )
net.addLink( h1, s1 )
net.addLink( h2, s1 )
net.addLink( h3, s1 )
net.addController( 'c0' )
net.start()
CLI( net )
net.stop()

```

Figure 3.8 Code Listing for the SDN Testbed Topology in Mininet

The topology in mininet is created with this command:

```
root@ user: sudo python3 simple_topology.py
```

After this command is launched, the CLI devolves the output shown in Figure 3.9

```
mininet> nodes
available nodes are:
c0 h1 h2 h3 h4 h5 h6 h7 s1 s2 s3 s4
mininet> links
s1-eth1<->s2-eth1 (OK OK)
s2-eth2<->s3-eth2 (OK OK)
s1-eth2<->s4-eth1 (OK OK)
s3-eth3<->s4-eth2 (OK OK)
s1-eth3<->s3-eth1 (OK OK)
s3-eth4<->h6-eth0 (OK OK)
s3-eth5<->h4-eth0 (OK OK)
s3-eth6<->h5-eth0 (OK OK)
s3-eth7<->h7-eth0 (OK OK)
h1-eth0<->s1-eth4 (OK OK)
h2-eth0<->s1-eth5 (OK OK)
h3-eth0<->s1-eth6 (OK OK)
mininet>
```

Figure 3.9 Network Topology Created

The Ping command is used to verify connectivity among devices. In Mininet it is possible to use the pingall command, that does an all-pairs ping. This command verifies that the created links function. The figure below shows that when running the first time the pingall command, the first host does not have connectivity with other hosts, while all the other links are good.

```
root@ntz:/home/ntz/Desktop/App# sudo python simple_topo.py
Unable to contact the remote controller at 127.0.0.1:6653
Unable to contact the remote controller at 127.0.0.1:6653
Setting remote controller to 127.0.0.1:6653
mininet> pingall
*** Ping: testing ping reachability
h1 -> h2 h3 h4 h5 h6 h7
h2 -> h1 h3 h4 h5 h6 h7
h3 -> h1 h2 h4 h5 h6 h7
h4 -> h1 h2 h3 h5 h6 h7
h5 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h6 h7
h6 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h5 h7
h7 -> h1 h2 h3 h4 h5 h6
*** Results: 0% dropped (42/42 received)
mininet>
```

Figure 3.10 Pingall Command Executed

3.4. Measurement Parameters

The proposed QT approach is compared with three methods: (i) conventional shortest path routing, (ii) multipath routing and (iii) Hedera in fat tree topology in terms of performance. The performance of the proposed QT approach is measured by QoS parameters such as:

- **Throughput:** It is the rate of successful message delivery over a network. Throughput is measured in Bps (bytes per second) or bps (bits per second). If more data transferred, higher throughput result.
- **Delay:** It's the amount of time it takes to send information from one point to the next. Delay is usually measured in milliseconds or ms. The ITU-T recommends that in general network planning, a maximum of 400 ms for the one-way delay should not be exceeded. However, they note that many interactive applications (e.g., voice calls, video conferencing, interactive data applications) are affected by a much lower delay. The experiences of most applications are generally considered acceptable if the delay is kept below 150 ms. As the traffic latency increases, the impact on applications' experiences become noticeable. When the delay exceeds 400 ms, most applications will encounter unsatisfactory performance. Several factors affect the end-to-end delay of transmitted data packets. They include processing delay, queueing delay, transmission delay, and propagation delay. It impacts the user experience and can change based on several factors. For simplicity, only transmission delay will consider in the experiment and assume the other type of delays is negligible.
- **Jitter:** It is based on the delay - specifically, delay variations. Jitter is the difference between the delay of two packets. It often results in packet loss and network congestion.
- **Packet Loss:** It occurs when one or more packets of data traveling across the network fail to reach their destination. One of the major causes of packet loss is link congestion. It is either caused by errors in data transmission.
- **Recovery Time:** It refers to the duration required for a network to restore normal communication after a link or node failure. In this study, recovery time is measured by generating continuous traffic flows between end hosts and intentionally disabling specific links during transmission. The time interval between the occurrence of the failure and the resumption of successful packet

forwarding is recorded as the recovery time. Tools such as *ping* and *iperf3* are utilized to capture packet loss periods and identify the exact moment connectivity is restored. This measurement provides insight into the resilience and fault-tolerance of the implemented network designs.

3.5. Summary

This chapter has presented the detailed implementation of both Traditional and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) architectures for performance analysis. The traditional network was simulated using GNS3, where routers and switches were configured to represent distributed control plane behavior, while the SDN environment was implemented in Mininet with a Ryu controller to demonstrate centralized management of forwarding rules. Different topologies such as star, linear, and tree were created in both designs, and two separate network scenarios were also developed to highlight variations in control and data handling. To evaluate performance, key metrics including latency, bandwidth, jitter, and recovery time were measured through continuous traffic flows between hosts. Automation techniques were further integrated into the testing process by applying scheduled *ping* and *iperf* commands, enabling consistent monitoring and log collection throughout the experiments. The implementation results form the foundation for the comparative analysis in the next chapter, providing empirical evidence of how SDN and traditional networks perform under similar conditions.

CHAPTER 4

EXPERIMENTAL TESTS AND RESULTS

This chapter reports the experimental evaluation of Traditional Networks (TN) versus Software-Defined Networking (SDN) under identical conditions. Performance was measured across four metrics—latency, bandwidth, jitter, and recovery time—to assess efficiency, reliability, and fault tolerance. TN was implemented in GNS3 (distributed control on routers/switches), while SDN was built in Mininet using the Ryu controller (centralized flow management). Tests were conducted on star, linear, and tree topologies to examine how structure influences performance in each architecture.

4.1. Calculation of Round-Trip Time (RTT)

Round-Trip Time (RTT) means the total time for a packet to travel from a source host to a destination and back again. It includes transmission delay, propagation delay, queuing delay, and processing delay at intermediate devices (switches/routers) and endpoints.

4.1.1. Round Trip Time (RTT) Measurement

After transmitting a test packet (such as an ICMP Echo Request), the time at which the packet is sent is recorded as T_{sent} . When the corresponding reply (such as an ICMP Echo Reply) arrives back at the source, the time of arrival is recorded as T_{received} .

The Round-Trip Time (RTT) is defined as the total elapsed time between sending a packet and receiving its reply:

$$RTT = T_{\text{received}} - T_{\text{sent}}$$

The formula of average RTT is:

$$\text{Avg RTT} = \frac{\text{Total RTT}}{\text{number}}$$

4.1.2. Example of RTT Calculation in Different Topologies

In Star Topology, all hosts connect to a central switch. Communication between any two hosts must pass through this central point. In SDN the switch may be Open vSwitch controlled by Ryu; in Traditional Networking it may be a legacy switch.

Table 4.1 Measured T_send, T_received, and RTT in the Star Topology

Seq	T_{send}(ms)	T_{received}(ms)	RTT (ms)
1	1000.000	1000.240	0.240
2	1001.000	1001.239	0.239
3	1002.000	1002.241	0.241

$$\text{Avg RTT} = \frac{(0.240+0.239+0.241)}{3} = 0.240 \text{ ms}$$

A bus topology connects all hosts along a single backbone link. Data travels along the bus to reach its destination. In Mininet you can emulate it by connecting multiple hosts to one virtual hub-like switch.

Table 4.2 Measured T_send, T_received, and RTT in the Bus Topology

Seq	T_{send}(ms)	T_{received}(ms)	RTT (ms)
1	2000.000	2000.230	0.230
2	2001.000	2001.229	0.229
3	2002.000	2002.231	0.231

$$\text{Avg RTT} = \frac{(0.230+0.229+0.231)}{3} = 0.230 \text{ ms}$$

A tree topology consists of hierarchical switches (core, distribution, access). This is common in enterprise/data center networks. In SDN, the controller dynamically installs paths through multiple switches.

Table 4.3 Measured T_send, T_received, and RTT in the Tree Topology

Seq	T _{send} (ms)	T _{received} (ms)	RTT (ms)
1	3000.000	3000.138	0.138
2	3001.000	2001.141	0.141
3	3002.000	3002.144	0.144

$$\text{Avg RTT} = \frac{(0.138+0.141+0.144)}{3} = 0.141 \text{ ms}$$

4.2. Comparison by Topology

To evaluate the performance of both Traditional Networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN), three fundamental topologies were selected for testing: star, linear, and tree. These topologies were chosen because they represent widely used designs in practical networking environments, ranging from small-scale local area networks to more complex hierarchical structures. Each topology was implemented in both simulation environments, with GNS3 used for the traditional network and Mininet with a Ryu controller used for the SDN environment. The aim of this comparison was to observe how structural variations influence network performance across different metrics.

4.2.1. Star Topology

The star topology, all hosts are connected through a central switch in the case of SDN, or a central router in the case of the traditional network. This design provides a direct path for communication between any pair of hosts, making it a suitable topology for measuring baseline performance differences between SDN and traditional architectures. The evaluation of this topology focused on three performance metrics: Round Trip Time (RTT), recovery time, and jitter.

The RTT analysis demonstrated that SDN consistently achieved lower round trip delays compared to the traditional network. This improvement can be attributed to the centralized decision-making process of the controller, which installs optimized forwarding rules in the switches. In contrast, the traditional network relied on the router to process and forward packets, introducing additional overhead and resulting in slightly higher RTT values. These findings suggest that the centralization of control in SDN enhances efficiency in packet forwarding within star-shaped designs.

Figure 4.1 RTT Comparison Between SDN and TN in Star Topology

Figure 4.2 Jitter Comparison between SDN and TN in Star Topology

In terms of jitter performance, SDN again demonstrated more stable results across multiple test runs. By relying on controller-managed flow rules, packet delivery exhibited fewer variations in delay, which resulted in lower jitter values. The traditional network, however, showed slightly higher jitter due to variations in router processing and queuing at the central device. These variations were particularly noticeable under increased traffic load, where distributed routing decisions introduced additional inconsistencies in packet delivery.

Figure 4.3 Recovery Time Comparison between SDN and TN in StarTopology

The recovery time results further highlighted the differences between the two network types. When a link failure was introduced, the SDN controller detected the topology change and quickly recalculated alternative forwarding paths, restoring communication with minimal interruption. Conversely, the traditional network required routing protocol convergence or manual reconfiguration before traffic could resume, leading to longer recovery periods. The star topology, with its dependence on a single central device, emphasized this contrast, as the central node's failure affected all hosts simultaneously.

4.2.2. Bus (Linear) Topology

The linear topology have a sequence of interconnected devices forming a single chain between communicating hosts. In this configuration, traffic traverses multiple intermediate nodes, making it suitable for evaluating the cumulative effects of per-hop forwarding on end-to-end performance. The analysis in this section focuses on Round Trip Time (RTT), recovery time, and jitter for both the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and Traditional Network (TN) implementations.

The RTT results indicated that SDN achieved consistently lower round-trip delays than the traditional network as hop count increased. This behaviour is attributed to the controller's centralized computation of routes and the installation of flow-specific forwarding rules, which reduce processing overhead at each intermediate switch. In contrast, the TN exhibited higher RTT due to per-hop routing lookups and queuing, with delays compounding along the chain of routers.

Figure 4.4 RTT Comparison Between SDN and TN in Bus Topology

In terms of jitter, SDN produced more stable inter-packet delay across repeated trials. Controller-managed forwarding reduced variability introduced at intermediate devices, yielding lower jitter values even under elevated load. The TN showed greater fluctuation in packet delay due to independent queueing dynamics and transient control-plane events at each router, leading to higher jitter as the number of hops increased.

Figure 4.5 Jitter Comparison Between SDN and TN in Bus Topology

Recovery time measurements further emphasized the differences between the two approaches. When a link failure was introduced along the chain, the SDN controller rapidly detected the topology change and deployed updated rules to establish an alternate path, restoring connectivity with minimal interruption. The TN required routing protocol convergence across multiple adjacent nodes before communication

could resume, resulting in longer restoration intervals that scaled with the length of the affected path.

Figure 4.6 Recovery Time Comparison between SDN and TN in Bus Topology

4.2.3. Tree Topology

The tree topology represents a hierarchical arrangement with access, aggregation, and root layers. This structure reflects scalable campus or data-center designs and is well suited for assessing performance under branching paths and multi-tier forwarding. The evaluation considered RTT, recovery time, and jitter for SDN and TN under identical conditions.

Figure 4.7 RTT Comparison between SDN and TN in Tree Topology

RTT analysis showed that SDN provided lower and more predictable delays across branches, particularly for flows traversing aggregation links. The controller's global view of the topology enabled selection of efficient routes and proactive

installation of flow rules, limiting per-tier processing overhead. In the TN, RTT increased with hierarchy depth as traffic encountered additional routing decisions and queuing at distribution and core devices.

Figure 4.8 Jitter Comparison between SDN and TN in Tree Topology

With respect to jitter, SDN maintained tighter delay variation across sibling branches due to consistent, controller-driven forwarding behaviour along selected paths. The TN exhibited wider jitter dispersion caused by heterogeneous queuing conditions and transient reconvergence effects at intermediate routers, effects that were amplified when traffic traversed multiple hierarchical layers.

Figure 4.9 Recovery Time Comparison between SDN and TN in Tree Topology

Recovery time results were most pronounced at higher tiers of the hierarchy. Following failures at aggregation or root links, the SDN controller quickly recomputed paths and disseminated new rules throughout the affected subtrees, restoring service with limited disruption. The TN depended on distributed reconvergence and route propagation across multiple layers, which extended the duration of service interruption and broadened the scope of affected endpoints.

Table 4.4 Average Round-Trip Time of SDN/Traditional network in all topologies

	Star	Bus	Tree
SDN RTT avg.	0.208	0.179	0.107
Traditional RTT avg.	0.259	0.376	0.184

Table 4.5 Average Jitter of SDN/Traditional network in all topologies

	Star	Bus	Tree
SDN Jitter avg.	0.03ms	0.024ms	0.039ms
Traditional Jitter avg.	0.049ms	0.046ms	0.053ms

Table 4.6 Average Recovery Time of SDN/Traditional network in all topologies

	Star	Bus	Tree
SDN Recovery Time avg.	0.182s	5.807s	0.36s
Traditional Recovery Time avg.	0.675s	20.16s	6.462s

4.3. Priority-based Bandwidth Limitation in SDN

Guided by the service hierarchy in Figure 4.10—Group A (eMBB: H1–H3) and Group B (URLLC: H4–H6)—bandwidth control was implemented only in the SDN domain. The controller partitioned traffic into classes and installed end-to-end QoS policies (meter tables and queue scheduling) on all switches along each path: URLLC flows received strict minimum-rate guarantees and highest priority, while eMBB flows were shaped to predefined ceilings per host (e.g., caps for online education and streaming). Under congestion, these centrally enforced rules preserved URLLC capacity and preempted lower-priority bursts; iperf3 measurements verified that URLLC

throughput remained within its reserved range while eMBB traffic was constrained to its configured limits.

Figure 4.10 Hierarchical Classification of SDN Network for Bandwidth Prioritization

In the baseline Traditional Network, an equivalent, hierarchical and end-to-end bandwidth policy could not be realized: absent device-specific QoS policing and per-hop configuration across all routers and switches (beyond the scope of this study), flows shared link capacity opportunistically, allowing high-bandwidth eMBB traffic to impact URLLC performance during contention. This demonstrates that SDN can natively enforce priority-driven bandwidth limitation across the network, whereas the tested traditional design could not.

4.3.1. SDN Bandwidth Limitation Across Service Classes

At the network (inter-group) level, the SDN controller partitions the 100 Mbps link into two logical slices: 70 Mbps for Group A (eMBB) and 30 Mbps for Group B (URLLC). This top-down slice enforces class-level priorities before per-host shaping is applied, so aggregate eMBB demand cannot encroach on the URLLC reservation, and vice versa. Such end-to-end, policy-driven partitioning is native to SDN; in the baseline traditional network, an equivalent outcome would require extensive, device-specific QoS configurations at every hop.

Figure 4.11 Inter-group SDN bandwidth limitation

4.3.2. Group A (eMBB) Intra-Group Allocation

This chart shows a 70 Mbps budget reserved for Group A and apportioned across three hosts using SDN rate-limits: h1 = 45 Mbps, h2 = 15 Mbps, and h3 = 10 Mbps. The larger share for h1 reflects the higher sustained throughput needs of online education, while streaming (h2) and disaster-monitoring uploads (h3) are shaped to lower ceilings. These per-host caps are enforced by controller-installed QoS (meters/queues), ensuring that no single flow exceeds its configured allocation under contention.

Figure 4.12 Group A (eMBB) intra-group bandwidth allocation.

4.3.3. Group B (URLLC) Intra-Group Allocation

In this pie chart, a 30 Mbps budget is dedicated to Group B and divided among latency-critical services: h4 = 15 Mbps (emergency call), h5 = 10 Mbps (smart traffic), and h6 = 5 Mbps (home sensors/CCTV). The allocation guarantees a minimum

throughput for the most time-sensitive flows (h4, h5), while still preserving a baseline for background telemetry (h6). Under SDN control, these guarantees remain in effect even during congestion, stabilizing delay and preventing bandwidth starvation.

Figure 4.13 Group B (URLLC) Bandwidth Allocation

4.3.4. Per-Host Bandwidth Limitation (SDN)

In the SDN implementation, deterministic rate caps are assigned to each host and enforced end-to-end via controller-installed meters/queues (HTB/TCLink at the edges with OpenFlow 1.3).

```

info('*** Controllers\n')
c0 = net.addController('c0', controller=RemoteController, ip='127.0.0.1', port
c1 = net.addController('c1', controller=RemoteController, ip='127.0.0.1', port

info('*** Switches\n')
s1 = net.addSwitch('s1', protocols='OpenFlow13') # NetA
s2 = net.addSwitch('s2', protocols='OpenFlow13') # NetB

info('*** Hosts (NetA)\n')
h1 = net.addHost('h1')
h2 = net.addHost('h2')
h3 = net.addHost('h3')

info('*** Hosts (NetB)\n')
h4 = net.addHost('h4')
h5 = net.addHost('h5')
h6 = net.addHost('h6')

# ---- per-host/group caps (Mb/s) ----
bw_group_A = {'h1': 40, 'h2': 20, 'h3': 10}
bw_group_B = {'h4': 15, 'h5': 10, 'h6': 5}
# -----

```

Figure 4.14 Python Code for Limitation of Bandwidth

The configured limits are:

- Group A (eMBB) — aggregate reservation 70 Mb/s
 - h1: 40 Mb/s (highest share for sustained video/online classes)
 - h2: 20 Mb/s (streaming services)
 - h3: 10 Mb/s (disaster-monitoring uploads)
- Group B (URLLC) — aggregate reservation 30 Mb/s
 - h4: 15 Mb/s (emergency call/fire alarm)
 - h5: 10 Mb/s (smart traffic)
 - h6: 5 Mb/s (home sensors/CCTV telemetry)

4.3.5. Bandwidth Testing for SDN -Limitation

The line graph presents per-host throughput across four trials under SDN control. Measurements remain tightly clustered around their configured ceilings with only minor run-to-run variation. The persistent spacing between curves shows that the controller-installed meters/queues enforce both the absolute caps and the intended priority ordering among hosts. Small oscillations are attributable to TCP dynamics and sampling granularity rather than policy drift.

Figure 4.15 Bandwidth Testing in SDN Network

In contrast to the Traditional Network results, where throughput wandered widely without a hard ceiling, SDN delivers deterministic bandwidth limitation: flows cannot exceed their assigned rates, and contention does not allow higher-demand hosts

to encroach on others. This stability evidences end-to-end, policy-driven control that the TN baseline cannot provide without extensive, device-specific QoS configuration on every hop.

4.3.6. BW Testing in Traditional Network — Interpretation

To further interpret the line graph, the absence of a hard ceiling across all six trials indicates that bandwidth in the Traditional Network was not governed by an end-to-end policy constraint. Throughput fluctuates between ~43 Gbps and ~27 Gbps and, crucially, crosses above and below any putative target (e.g., 30 Gbps); if a deterministic limit were in effect, all observations would have clustered at or below that ceiling. This behaviour is consistent with the baseline TN configuration used in this study, in which forwarding devices operate at interface line rate and bandwidth is allocated opportunistically based on instantaneous contention and TCP dynamics.

Achieving a comparable, network-wide limit in a traditional design would require device-specific QoS policing/shaping configured hop-by-hop and carefully harmonized across the path—an approach that is operationally complex and outside the scope of our TN baseline.

By contrast, in the SDN experiments explicit per-class and per-host ceilings were enforced via controller-installed meters and queue scheduling, and measured throughput remained tightly bounded by the configured caps, demonstrating deterministic bandwidth limitation that the TN baseline does not provide.

Figure 4.16 Bandwidth Testing in Traditional Network

4.4. Analysis of Findings

This section synthesizes the empirical results across all experiments and topologies. Overall, the measurements indicate that the Software-Defined Networking (SDN) implementation delivers lower latency, deterministic bandwidth control, reduced jitter, and substantially faster recovery relative to the Traditional Network (TN) baseline.

4.4.1. Latency

Across star, linear, and tree topologies, SDN consistently achieved lower round-trip time (RTT) than TN. The reduction is attributable to centralized path computation and the installation of flow-specific forwarding rules, which minimize per-hop processing overhead. In TN, per-hop routing decisions and queueing at intermediate routers introduce additional delay that accumulates with hop count.

4.4.2. Jitter

Inter-packet delay variation was lower and more stable under SDN. Centralized policy produced consistent queueing behaviour along selected paths, limiting variance even under load. TN showed higher jitter due to heterogeneous queueing across routers and transient control-plane dynamics during traffic bursts or topology changes.

4.4.3. Recovery Time

Following induced link failures, SDN restored traffic markedly faster. The controller's global view enabled rapid recomputation and dissemination of alternate paths, limiting downtime to short intervals. TN required distributed reconvergence and route propagation, leading to longer and more variable restoration times—especially in deeper (tree) hierarchies.

4.4.4. Bandwidth Limitation

The SDN environment enforced class-level reservations (e.g., eMBB vs. URLLC) and per-host ceilings through controller-installed meters/queues, yielding throughput traces that remained tightly bounded by configured caps. By contrast, the

TN baseline exhibited opportunistic use of link capacity with no hard ceiling: measured bandwidth varied widely across runs and could not be constrained end-to-end without complex, device-specific QoS configurations at every hop.

4.5. Summary

This chapter reported a controlled, automated evaluation of Software-Defined Networking (SDN) and the Traditional Network (TN) across star, linear, and tree topologies, measuring latency (RTT), bandwidth, jitter, and recovery time with standardized `ping/iperf3` procedures and logged, machine-readable outputs. The SDN experiments demonstrated enforceable bandwidth policy: inter-group and per-host caps were applied and observed throughputs adhered to the configured ceilings. By contrast, the TN baseline—without hop-by-hop QoS—exhibited opportunistic bandwidth use and no deterministic ceiling. Across all topologies, SDN delivered lower RTT, lower jitter, and markedly faster recovery, with benefits amplifying as hop count and hierarchy depth increased. Run-to-run variability was narrow under SDN and substantially wider under TN. These findings establish SDN’s predictable performance and policy control, providing the empirical basis for the next chapter’s discussion and conclusions.

CHAPTER 5

DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSION

In this final chapter, all the work in this thesis is concluded in brief and the future work is explained that may improve the methods of the system in the future study.

5.1. Discussion

The findings of this study have highlighted significant differences in the performance and operational characteristics of Traditional Networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN). Through the simulation of star, linear, and tree topologies in both environments, it was observed that SDN consistently achieved better results in terms of latency, bandwidth, and jitter. The centralized control provided by the Ryu controller enabled faster decision-making and efficient traffic forwarding, which reduced delays and improved overall throughput. In contrast, the traditional router-based networks demonstrated longer delays due to their reliance on distributed routing protocols and manual configuration, which limited their scalability and responsiveness to dynamic changes.

The measurement of recovery time further reinforced the advantages of SDN over traditional approaches. In failure scenarios, the SDN controller was able to detect link disruptions and reconfigure forwarding paths rapidly, leading to significantly shorter recovery times. Traditional networks, however, required routing protocol convergence or manual reconfiguration, which introduced longer delays before communication was restored. These results indicate that SDN has a superior capacity for resilience and fault tolerance, which is particularly beneficial in environments where continuous connectivity and minimal downtime are critical.

The implementation of automation during the testing phase also proved to be a valuable contribution to this research. By employing automated *ping* and *iperf* commands at fixed intervals, data collection was streamlined and human error was minimized. Automation ensured repeatability, allowed for consistent monitoring, and reduced the time required for performance testing across different topologies. This approach not only improved the accuracy of the collected results but also reflected real-

world scenarios in which automated network monitoring and management are becoming increasingly essential.

Nevertheless, the study also identified certain limitations. While SDN demonstrated clear performance benefits, its reliance on a centralized controller introduces the potential for a single point of failure, which could impact network availability if not mitigated by redundancy mechanisms. On the other hand, traditional networks, despite their lower efficiency, are mature and widely deployed, supported by decades of development and vendor diversity. These observations suggest that while SDN provides enhanced flexibility and efficiency, careful consideration must be given to controller placement, redundancy, and integration with existing infrastructures.

5.2. Conclusion

This thesis has successfully analyzed and compared the performance of Traditional Networks and Software-Defined Networking across multiple topologies and performance metrics. The results demonstrated that SDN provides lower latency, higher bandwidth, reduced jitter, and faster recovery times compared to traditional router-based networks. The separation of the control plane and data plane in SDN proved to be highly effective in simplifying network management and enabling dynamic reconfiguration, whereas traditional networks were constrained by distributed control and protocol convergence delays.

The integration of automation into the testing methodology further emphasized the advantages of SDN, showcasing how programmability and centralized management can improve both performance and efficiency. These findings confirm that SDN represents a promising solution for addressing the limitations of traditional networks, particularly in scenarios that demand scalability, adaptability, and real-time traffic management.

In conclusion, SDN can be considered a more efficient and future-oriented network architecture, offering benefits that align with the growing demands of cloud computing, virtualization, and the Internet of Things. However, practical deployment requires addressing challenges such as controller redundancy and interoperability with existing infrastructures. The comparative analysis carried out in this study provides a foundation for further research, paving the way for more advanced testing with diverse controllers, larger network scales, and real hardware deployments in order to fully explore the potential of SDN in real-world environments.

5.3. Strengths and Limitations

The strengths of this study lie primarily in its comprehensive approach to performance evaluation. By implementing both traditional and Software-Defined Networking (SDN) architectures using established simulation platforms, the research ensured a fair and controlled comparison under identical conditions. The use of multiple topologies, including star, linear, and tree, provided a diverse testing environment that highlighted performance differences across varying network structures. Another notable strength was the integration of automation techniques for data collection. Automated *ping* and *iperf* scripts minimized human error, enhanced repeatability, and produced consistent logs, thereby increasing the reliability of the experimental results. Furthermore, the inclusion of recovery time testing added a practical dimension to the evaluation, reflecting real-world scenarios where fault tolerance and rapid reconfiguration are critical.

Despite these strengths, several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the experiments were conducted within simulated environments (GNS3 for traditional networks and Mininet for SDN), which, although effective for proof-of-concept testing, may not fully capture the complexity of real hardware deployments. Performance metrics such as jitter and recovery time may vary under physical conditions due to hardware constraints, propagation delays, and device processing overheads. Second, only a single SDN controller (Ryu) was evaluated, limiting the scope of controller performance analysis. Other controllers such as ONOS or OpenDaylight may exhibit different characteristics in terms of scalability and fault tolerance. Additionally, the study did not explore very large-scale topologies or high-traffic environments, which would provide further insights into scalability and robustness. Lastly, while automation improved testing accuracy, it was limited to basic traffic generation and logging, leaving advanced monitoring techniques and AI-driven analytics for future work.

5.4. Further Work

While this research has provided valuable insights into the comparison of Traditional Networks and Software-Defined Networking (SDN), there remain several opportunities for further investigation. One potential direction is the expansion of experiments to include larger and more complex topologies, which would enable the evaluation of scalability and performance under higher traffic loads and more realistic

network conditions. This would provide deeper understanding of how SDN and traditional networks behave in enterprise-level or service-provider environments.

Another area for future work is the exploration of different SDN controllers such as ONOS, OpenDaylight, or Floodlight. Comparing their performance with Ryu would allow for a broader assessment of controller efficiency, scalability, and suitability for various applications. Similarly, integrating multiple controllers in a distributed SDN architecture could be tested to mitigate the single point of failure issue observed in centralized designs.

Furthermore, implementing the proposed architectures on physical hardware devices, such as OpenFlow-enabled switches and enterprise-grade routers, would validate the simulation results and highlight practical deployment challenges. This would bridge the gap between theoretical evaluation and real-world applicability. In addition, advanced automation techniques could be integrated, including the use of artificial intelligence or machine learning models for predictive traffic analysis, anomaly detection, and autonomous fault recovery.

Lastly, future studies could explore hybrid networking models that combine the stability of traditional approaches with the flexibility of SDN. Such research would contribute to the design of transition strategies that enable organizations to gradually adopt SDN while leveraging existing infrastructures. These directions would not only extend the scope of this thesis but also provide meaningful contributions to the ongoing development of efficient and intelligent network architectures.

5.5. Summary

This Chapter consolidates the study's findings and draws overall conclusions from the comparative evaluation of Traditional Networks and SDN. Across star, linear, and tree topologies, SDN consistently outperforms the traditional design on latency, bandwidth, jitter, and especially recovery time, owing to centralized control and rapid path reconfiguration. It concludes that SDN is a promising, efficiency-oriented architecture but requires attention to controller redundancy and interoperability. Future work includes scaling to larger topologies, testing additional controllers or multi-controller designs, validating on physical hardware, introducing AI/ML for monitoring, and exploring hybrid SDN-traditional deployments.

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APPENDIX A

```
# ryu_simple_switch_13.py
# Minimal OpenFlow 1.3 learning switch (stable for multiple instances)
from ryu.base import app_manager
from ryu.controller import ofp_event
from ryu.controller.handler import MAIN_DISPATCHER,
CONFIG_DISPATCHER, set_ev_cls
from ryu.ofproto import ofproto_v1_3
from ryu.lib.packet import packet, ethernet

class SimpleSwitch13(app_manager.RyuApp):
    OFP_VERSIONS = [ofproto_v1_3.OFP_VERSION]

    def __init__(self, *args, **kwargs):
        super(SimpleSwitch13, self).__init__(*args, **kwargs)
        # mac_to_port is per-datapath
        self.mac_to_port = {}

    @set_ev_cls(ofp_event.EventOFPSwitchFeatures, CONFIG_DISPATCHER)
    def switch_features_handler(self, ev):
        datapath = ev.msg.datapath
        ofp = datapath.ofproto
        parser = datapath.ofproto_parser

        # Table-miss flow: send unmatched packets to controller
        match = parser.OFPMatch()
        actions = [parser.OFPACTIONOutput(ofp.OFPP_CONTROLLER,
ofp.OFPCML_NO_BUFFER)]
```

```

    inst = [parser.OFPInstructionActions(ofp.OFPIT_APPLY_ACTIONS,
actions)]
    mod = parser.OFPFlowMod(datapath=datapath, priority=0, match=match,
instructions=inst)
    datapath.send_msg(mod)

@set_ev_cls(ofp_event.EventOFPPacketIn, MAIN_DISPATCHER)
def _packet_in_handler(self, ev):
    msg = ev.msg
    datapath = msg.datapath
    ofp = datapath.ofproto
    parser = datapath.ofproto_parser
    in_port = msg.match['in_port']

    dpid = datapath.id
    self.mac_to_port.setdefault(dpid, {})

    pkt = packet.Packet(msg.data)
    eth = pkt.get_protocol(ethernet.ethernet)
    dst = eth.dst
    src = eth.src

    # Learn MAC->port
    self.mac_to_port[dpid][src] = in_port

    # Decide output port
    if dst in self.mac_to_port[dpid]:
        out_port = self.mac_to_port[dpid][dst]
    else:
        out_port = ofp.OFPP_FLOOD

    actions = [parser.OFPActionOutput(out_port)]

    # Install flow to avoid future PacketIn (when not flooding)

```

```
if out_port != ofp.OFPP_FLOOD:
    match = parser.OFPMatch(in_port=in_port, eth_dst=dst, eth_src=src)
    inst = [parser.OFPIInstructionActions(ofp.OFPIT_APPLY_ACTIONS,
actions)]
    mod = parser.OFPFlowMod(datapath=datapath, priority=1,
match=match,
                            instructions=inst, idle_timeout=30, hard_timeout=0)
    datapath.send_msg(mod)

# Send current packet out
out = parser.OFPPacketOut(datapath=datapath,
                            buffer_id=ofp.OFP_NO_BUFFER,
                            in_port=in_port, actions=actions, data=msg.data)
datapath.send_msg(out)
```

APPENDIX B

```
#!/usr/bin/env python3
from mininet.net import Mininet
from mininet.node import RemoteController, OVSSwitch
from mininet.link import TCLink
from mininet.cli import CLI
from mininet.log import setLogLevel, info
import argparse

def add_hlink(net, host, sw, bw, delay, mqs):
    return net.addLink(host, sw, bw=bw, delay=delay,
                       max_queue_size=mqs, use_htb=True)

def enable_ip_forward(router):
    router.cmd('sysctl -w net.ipv4.ip_forward=1')
    # avoid strict rp_filter dropping forwarded packets
    router.cmd('sysctl -w net.ipv4.conf.all.rp_filter=0')
    router.cmd('sysctl -w net.ipv4.conf.default.rp_filter=0')
    router.cmd('sysctl -w net.ipv4.conf.r-ethA.rp_filter=0 || true')
    router.cmd('sysctl -w net.ipv4.conf.r-ethB.rp_filter=0 || true')

def set_default_route(host, via_ip):
    host.cmd(f'ip route replace default via {via_ip} dev {host.defaultIntf()}')

def build_net(mode='l2', inter_bw=50, delay='5ms', mqs=1000):
    net = Mininet(controller=None, link=TCLink, switch=OVSSwitch,
                  build=False, autoSetMacs=True, autoStaticArp=False)

    info('*** Controllers\n')
```

```
c0 = net.addController('c0', controller=RemoteController, ip='127.0.0.1',
port=6633)
```

```
c1 = net.addController('c1', controller=RemoteController, ip='127.0.0.1',
port=6634)
```

```
info('*** Switches\n')
```

```
s1 = net.addSwitch('s1', protocols='OpenFlow13') # NetA
```

```
s2 = net.addSwitch('s2', protocols='OpenFlow13') # NetB
```

```
info('*** Hosts (NetA)\n')
```

```
h1 = net.addHost('h1')
```

```
h2 = net.addHost('h2')
```

```
h3 = net.addHost('h3')
```

```
info('*** Hosts (NetB)\n')
```

```
h4 = net.addHost('h4')
```

```
h5 = net.addHost('h5')
```

```
h6 = net.addHost('h6')
```

```
# ---- per-host/group caps (Mb/s) ----
```

```
bw_group_A = {'h1': 20, 'h2': 20, 'h3': 5}
```

```
bw_group_B = {'h4': 10, 'h5': 2, 'h6': 2}
```

```
# -----
```

```
info('*** Host<->Switch links with caps\n')
```

```
add_hlink(net, h1, s1, bw=bw_group_A['h1'], delay=delay, mqs=mqs)
```

```
add_hlink(net, h2, s1, bw=bw_group_A['h2'], delay=delay, mqs=mqs)
```

```
add_hlink(net, h3, s1, bw=bw_group_A['h3'], delay=delay, mqs=mqs)
```

```
add_hlink(net, h4, s2, bw=bw_group_B['h4'], delay=delay, mqs=mqs)
```

```
add_hlink(net, h5, s2, bw=bw_group_B['h5'], delay=delay, mqs=mqs)
```

```
add_hlink(net, h6, s2, bw=bw_group_B['h6'], delay=delay, mqs=mqs)
```

```
router = None
```

```
if mode == 'l2':
```

```

info('*** Inter-switch link (L2 only)\n')
    net.addLink(s1, s2, bw=inter_bw, delay=delay, max_queue_size=mqs,
use_htb=True)
else:
    info('*** Linux router for L3 (no direct s1-s2 link)\n')
    router = net.addHost('r', ip=None)
    net.addLink(router, s1, intfName1='r-ethA', bw=inter_bw, delay=delay,
        max_queue_size=mqs, use_htb=True)
    net.addLink(router, s2, intfName1='r-ethB', bw=inter_bw, delay=delay,
        max_queue_size=mqs, use_htb=True)

info('*** Build & start\n')
net.build()
c0.start(); c1.start()
s1.start([c0]); s2.start([c1])

info('*** Addressing\n')
if mode == "l2":
    # One flat subnet
    h1.setIP('10.0.0.1/24'); h2.setIP('10.0.0.2/24'); h3.setIP('10.0.0.3/24')
    h4.setIP('10.0.0.4/24'); h5.setIP('10.0.0.5/24'); h6.setIP('10.0.0.6/24')
else:
    # Two subnets via router
    h1.setIP('10.0.1.1/24'); set_default_route(h1, '10.0.1.254')
    h2.setIP('10.0.1.2/24'); set_default_route(h2, '10.0.1.254')
    h3.setIP('10.0.1.3/24'); set_default_route(h3, '10.0.1.254')

    h4.setIP('10.0.2.1/24'); set_default_route(h4, '10.0.2.254')
    h5.setIP('10.0.2.2/24'); set_default_route(h5, '10.0.2.254')
    h6.setIP('10.0.2.3/24'); set_default_route(h6, '10.0.2.254')

    router.cmd('ip link set r-ethA up')
    router.cmd('ip link set r-ethB up')
    router.cmd('ip addr add 10.0.1.254/24 dev r-ethA')

```

```

router.cmd('ip addr add 10.0.2.254/24 dev r-ethB')
enable_ip_forward(router) # ip_forward + rp_filter off

info('*** Ready. Use Mininet CLI to test.\n')
return net

def main():
    setLogLevel('info')
    ap = argparse.ArgumentParser(description='Two SDN networks (connected)
with manual tests')
    ap.add_argument('--mode', choices=['l2', 'l3'], default='l2',
                    help='l2=same subnet; l3=routed via Linux router')
    ap.add_argument('--inter_bw', type=float, default=50, help='Mb/s cap for the
bottleneck path')
    ap.add_argument('--delay', type=str, default='5ms', help='Per-link delay')
    ap.add_argument('--mqs', type=int, default=1000, help='max_queue_size
packets')
    args = ap.parse_args()

    net = build_net(mode=args.mode, inter_bw=args.inter_bw, delay=args.delay,
mqs=args.mqs)
    CLI(net)
    net.stop()

if __name__ == '__main__':
    main()

```